

Research

Metamorphic evaluation and tectonic implications of Mozhugongka garnet amphibolites, Lhasa terrane, Tibet

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Abstract: The Mozhugongka garnet amphibolites exhibit mineral assemblage of garnet, amphibole, albite, quartz, phengite, epidote, rutile, and chlorite. Based on the metamorphic textures, two metamorphic stages (peak metamorphism: M2; retrograde metamorphism: M3) can be observed: M2: Grt + Hbl + Pl + Qz, M3: Hbl + Pl + Qz. Metamorphic P-T calculations were conducted by GHPQ and HPQ geothermobarometers for two garnet amphibolite samples. The results for M2 and M3 are ~15-16 kbar/550-580 °C and ~6-9 kbar/400-490 °C, respectively. Mozhugongka garnet amphibolites can be geochemically and geochronologically compared with the Bailang eclogites, as both Bailang eclogites and Mozhugongka amphibolites possess OIB affinity and share similar exhumation path. Based on geochemical and retrograde metamorphic similarities, Mozhugongka garnet amphibolites may have originated from eclogites, which also exhumed during Triassic (219±1.2 Ma) along with Pangna blueschist, Jilang, Songduo and Bailang eclogites. Mozhugongka garnet amphibolites possibly mark the westward extension of Songduo metamorphic complex along with Pangna blueschist.

Keywords: Mozhugongka, geothermobarometers, garnet amphibolite, eclogite, Tibet

1. Introduction

High pressure (HP)/low temperature (LT) metamorphic rocks exposed in subduction zones usually indicate the ancient boundary of plates and/or terranes and recycle of crustal materials (Smith, 1988; Erdman and Lee, 2014). In general, HP rocks exhumed as an entire block and share similar P-T paths (Ring and Glodny, 2010). They can provide valuable information about the characteristics of their protolith and the thermal texture of subduction zones (Erdman and Lee, 2014). During the past ten years, the Songduo, Bailang, and Jilang HP eclogites were reported from the Songduo metamorphic complex in east-central Lhasa terrane, and the Lhasa terrane may be divided into the North and South sub-terranes by a subduction system in the Permian (Fig.1; Cheng et al., 2012, 2015; Liu et al., 2009; Yang et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2019). Most of the previous studies conducted in the Songduo metamorphic complex are mainly on the geochemistry and metamorphic evolution of eclogite and blueschist (Cheng et al., 2012, 2015; Liu et al., 2009; Yang et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2019). Whether these mafic HP metamorphic rocks represent the Paleotethys relics and the westward extension of this HP metamorphic complex still remain controversial.

In this study, we focus on the Mozhuogongka garnet amphibolites, ~80 km west of Songduo, in terms of metamorphic evolution. Combined with previous published data of Songduo metamorphic rocks, we aim to illustrate the metamorphic processes and the relationships between garnet amphibolite and eclogite.

2. Geologic Settings

The Tibetan Plateau is mainly composed of Qaidam-Kunlun, Songpan-Ganzi, Qiangtang, and Lhasa terranes, which from north to south, are divided by Kunlun, Jinsha, Bangong-Nujiang and Yarlung Zangpo suture zones, respectively (Fig. 1a; Yin and Harrison 2000; Geng et al., 2006; Xu et al., 2006; Yin 2006; Zhang et al., 2012, 2018; Zhang and Zhang, 2017; Jin et al., 2019). The Lhasa terrane is positioned in the southern part of Tibet and is bordered by Bangong-Nujiang and Yarlung Zangpo suture zones (Chang et al., 1986; Yin and Harrison 2000). The Permo-Triassic Songduo eclogite-bearing metamorphic complex, which is interpreted to identify a Songduo subduction system (e.g., Yang et al., 2006, 2009), is mainly composed of eclogite, blueschist, mica schist, greenschist, marble, and quartzite (Yang et al., 2009). Lhasa terrane may record more than one event of oceanic spreading, subduction and continental collision in the array of Paleotethys Ocean (e.g., Zhang et al., 2019). N-MORB type Songduo eclogites along with the ultramafics

reported from south of Songduo subduction system helped to partition South and North Lhasa subterranean (Fig. 1a; Zhang et al., 2019). The Songduo and Jilang MORB-type eclogites demonstrating the peak eclogite-facies metamorphism ages of 265-261 Ma (Cheng et al., 2012; Yang et al., 2009). OIB-type eclogitic bodies have also been reported from Bailang area, displaying the eclogite-facies metamorphic age of 230-227 Ma (Cheng et al., 2015). It is suggested that in this area, Paleo-tethyan Ocean opening started in the early Permian and the ultimate closure of this ocean basin was not prior to 230 Ma (e.g., Zhang et al., 2019).

Fig. 1. (a) Tectonic map of Tibet (after Cheng et al., 2012). (b) Geologic map of the studied Mozhugongka area (after Geological Survey Institute of Xizang, 2007).

In the Mozhugongka area, the metamorphic complex comprises garnet amphibolite, blueschist, greenschist, marble, mica schist, and quartzite. This metamorphic complex was intruded by Triassic, Jurassic and Cretaceous igneous rocks (Fig. 1b; Zhu et al., 2013). Permian OIB type mafic rocks have also been reported from Wenmulang area in Songduo complex (Wang et al., 2019). Garnet amphibolite, blueschist, and quartzite occur as pods within gneiss and schist along the thrust faults (Fig. 1b). Especially, some garnet amphibolite, which may have been retrograded from eclogites, occurs as lenses within garnet muscovite schist (Figs. 1b, 3). The exposed garnet amphibolites show clear white-eye texture of plagioclase encircling the garnet (Fig. 3b).

3. Methodology

Mineral composition calculation was done by Electron Microprobe Analyzer (EPMA; JXA-8100, JEOL) for Mozhugongka amphibolites at Beijing Research Institute of Uranium Geology. This experiment was conducted at operating conditions of 15 kV accelerating voltage and 20 nA beam current. Beam diameter of 5 μm was adjusted in accordance with the mineral sizes. A large variety of artificial and synthetic minerals belonging to the SPI Company were used for standardization purpose and ZAF corrections were carried out. Results of the representative minerals are displayed in Table 1.

Fig.2. Chemical compositional profile for garnet from sample D2093-N

4. Results

4.1. Petrography and Mineral Chemistry

The garnet amphibolites is commonly composed of amphibole (25–45 vol%), plagioclase (30–50 vol%), garnet (15–35 vol%), quartz (5–15 vol%), phengite (5–20 vol%), rutile (5 vol%), chlorite (5 vol%), epidote (5 vol%) for both the samples D2093-N2 and D2093-N3 (Fig. 4). Albite/quartz combined with amphibole and chlorite needles wrap the garnet rim, illustrating a symplectite texture (Fig. 4b). Garnet is mainly subhedral to anhedral and fractured, demonstrating core to rim texture (Figs. 2, 4a, b). The chemistry of garnet fluctuates between $\text{alm}_{0.55-0.56} \text{prp}_{0.06-0.07} \text{grs}_{0.24-0.25} \text{sps}_{0.11-0.12}$ in the core to $\text{alm}_{0.61-0.63} \text{prp}_{0.07-0.08} \text{grs}_{0.23-0.26} \text{sps}_{0.04-0.07}$ in the rim (Table 1). Rutile, epidote and amphibole occur as inclusions in garnet (Fig. 4a, b).

Table 1. EMPA mineral chemistry data. Minerals abbreviations (Whitney and Evans, 2010).

Sample#	D2093-N2								
	Ts. Hbl	Ts. Hbl	Ts. Hbl	Ts. Hbl	Ab	Ab	Ph	Grt-Line1	Grt-Line2
	Matrix	Matrix	Matrix	Sym	Matrix	Sym	Matrix	Rim	Rim
SiO ₂	42.83	42.97	44.24	43.45	67.96	69.09	48.99	37.21	37.24
TiO ₂	0.48	2.07	0.41	0.36	0	0	0.36	0.05	0.17
Al ₂ O ₃	14.39	14.38	13.95	14.38	19.87	18.66	29.11	20.38	20.23
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.05	0.06	0.05	0	0	0.01	0.05	-	-
FeO	17.88	17.5	17.29	17.44	0.11	0.18	3.26	29.29	27.85
MnO	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.08	0.01	0.03	0	1.94	2.14
MgO	8.58	7.91	8.61	8.43	0	0.01	1.86	2.28	2.08
CaO	9.6	8.63	9.83	9.02	0.5	0.19	0.06	8.53	9.36
Na ₂ O	2.97	3.2	2.88	3.32	10.99	11.46	1.74	0.04	0.01
K ₂ O	0.55	0.5	0.5	0.51	0.04	0.02	9.57	-	0.02
NiO	-	-	0.01	-	0	0.02	-	-	0.03
Total	97.42	97.3	97.86	96.99	99.48	99.67	94.99	99.71	99.14
Si	6.43	6.43	6.57	6.52	3	3.04	3.3	2.99	3
Ti	0.05	0.23	0.05	0.04	0	0	0.02	0	0.01
Al	2.55	2.54	2.44	2.54	1.03	0.97	2.31	1.93	1.92
Cr	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Fe ^{tot}	2.25	2.19	2.15	2.19	0	0.01	0.18	1.97	1.88
Mn	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0	0	0	0.13	0.15
Mg	1.92	1.77	1.91	1.89	0	0	0.19	0.27	0.25
Ca	1.54	1.38	1.57	1.45	0.02	0.01	0	0.74	0.81
Na	0.86	0.93	0.83	0.96	0.94	0.98	0.23		
K	0.11	0.09	0.09	0.1	0	0	0.82		
Total	15.73	15.58	15.62	15.7	5	5	7.05	8.04	8.02
prp								8.1	7.6
alm								63.3	60.9
grs								23.6	26.2
sps								4.3	4.7
an					2.4				
ab					97.3				
or					0.2				

Sample#	D2093-N2								
	Grt-Line3	Grt-Line4	Grt-Line5	Grt-Line6	Grt-Line7	Grt-Line8	Grt-Line9	Grt-Line10	Grt-Line11
	Rim	Rim	Rim	Rim	Core	Core	Core	Core	Core
SiO ₂	36.85	37.15	37.27	37.58	37.25	37.23	37.33	37.04	37.06
TiO ₂	0.17	0.25	0.14	0.21	0.15	0.25	0.2	0.29	0.28
Al ₂ O ₃	20.46	20.07	20.05	19.75	19.91	20.06	20.13	19.88	20.27
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.03	-	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.01	-	-	0
FeO	28.38	27.89	27.16	26.22	26.15	25.74	25.72	25.64	26.29
MnO	2.87	3.7	4.35	5.03	5.44	5.27	5.1	5.56	5.2
MgO	1.98	1.91	1.89	1.81	1.78	1.76	1.85	1.47	1.79
CaO	8.97	8.85	8.89	9.09	8.57	9.24	9.22	9.29	8.95
Na ₂ O	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.02	0.03
K ₂ O	0.03	-	0.01	0.01	-	-	-	0.01	-
NiO	-	-	0.03	0	-	0.02	-	-	0
Total	99.76	99.84	99.82	99.76	99.31	99.61	99.59	99.2	99.87
Si	2.97	2.99	3	3.03	3.02	3	3.01	3	2.98
Ti	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02
Al	1.94	1.91	1.9	1.87	1.9	1.91	1.91	1.9	1.92
Cr									
Fe ^{tot}	1.91	1.88	1.83	1.77	1.77	1.74	1.73	1.74	1.77
Mn	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.34	0.37	0.36	0.35	0.38	0.35
Mg	0.24	0.23	0.23	0.22	0.22	0.21	0.22	0.18	0.21
Ca	0.77	0.76	0.77	0.78	0.74	0.8	0.8	0.81	0.77
Na									
K									
Total	8.1	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0
prp	7.3	7.3	7.0	6.9	6.8	7.2	5.7	6.9	6.4
alm	61.3	60.1	58.6	56.8	57.1	55.9	55.9	56.0	56.9
grs	24.8	24.4	24.6	25.2	24.0	25.7	25.7	26.0	24.8
sps	6.3	8.1	9.5	11.0	12.0	11.6	11.2	12.3	11.4

Sample#	D2093-N2								
	Grt-Line12	Grt-Line13	Grt-Line14	Grt-Line15	Grt-Line16	Grt-Line17	Grt-Line18	Grt-Line19	Grt-Line20
	Core	Core	Core	Rim	Rim	Rim	Rim	Rim	Rim
SiO ₂	37.01	37.17	36.99	37.77	37.77	37.45	37.83	37.41	38.19
TiO ₂	0.32	0.22	0.19	0.17	0.14	0.2	0.1	0.09	0.02
Al ₂ O ₃	20.34	20.33	20.41	20	20.15	20.38	20.24	20.08	20.1
Cr ₂ O ₃	-	0.02	-	-	0.05	-	0.02	-	0.02
FeO	25.95	26.55	26.49	26.66	26.99	27.69	28.33	29.55	27.94
MnO	4.85	4.62	4.5	4.2	3.86	2.77	2.25	1.84	1.93
MgO	1.66	1.89	1.89	1.86	1.7	1.9	2.1	2.24	2.25
CaO	9.43	9.15	8.9	9.11	9.27	9.58	8.95	8.63	8.75
Na ₂ O	0.06	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.03	-	0.02
K ₂ O	-	0	0.02	-	-	-	-	-	0.01
NiO	-	-	0.02	-	0.01	-	0.04	0.03	0.01
Total	99.61	99.98	99.43	99.79	99.95	99.99	99.89	99.87	99.23
Si	2.98	2.99	2.99	3.03	3.03	3	3.03	3.01	3.06
Ti	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0
Al	1.93	1.93	1.94	1.89	1.9	1.92	1.91	1.9	1.9
Cr									
Fe ^{tot}	1.75	1.78	1.79	1.79	1.81	1.85	1.9	1.99	1.87
Mn	0.33	0.31	0.31	0.29	0.26	0.19	0.15	0.12	0.13
Mg	0.2	0.23	0.23	0.22	0.2	0.23	0.25	0.27	0.27
Ca	0.81	0.79	0.77	0.78	0.8	0.82	0.77	0.74	0.75
Na									
K									
Total	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0
prp	7.3	7.3	7.2	6.6	7.3	8.2	8.6	8.9	
alm	56.5	57.3	57.8	58.1	58.9	60.0	61.8	63.6	61.9
grs	26.3	25.3	24.9	25.4	25.9	26.6	25.0	23.8	24.9
sps	10.7	10.1	10.0	9.3	8.5	6.1	5.0	4.0	4.3

Sample#	D2093-N3		
	Mhb	Mhb	Mhb
	Matrix	Sym	Sym
SiO ₂	46.65	44.54	45.59
TiO ₂	0.38	0.44	0.33
Al ₂ O ₃	12.42	12.78	12.13
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.02	0.01	-
FeO	15.22	16.61	16.44
MnO	0.14	0.09	0.11
MgO	10.22	9.61	9.85
CaO	8.02	9.2	9.25
Na ₂ O	3.62	3.32	3.33
K ₂ O	0.34	0.48	0.4
NiO	0.01	0	0.03
Total	97.04	97.07	97.46
Si	6.87	6.65	6.76
Ti	0.04	0.05	0.04
Al	2.15	2.25	2.12
Cr	0	0	0
Fe ^{tot}	1.87	2.07	2.04
Mn	0.02	0.01	0.01
Mg	2.24	2.14	2.18
Ca	1.27	1.47	1.47
Na	1.03	0.96	0.96
K	0.06	0.09	0.08
Total	15.6	15.7	15.7
ppp			
alm			
grs			
sps			

Fig. 3. Field photographs showing (a) garnet amphibolite enclosed in garnet-muscovite schist; (b) garnet amphibolite exhibiting retrograded texture of plagioclase surrounding garnet; (c) the studied amphibolite rock. Abbreviations of minerals are in accordance with Whitney and Evans (2010).

Amphiboles are subhedral to anhedral and are extremely small in size when found as inclusions in garnet (Figs. 4b, c). Variable chemistry of amphiboles can be observed in different samples (Table 1). According to classification of Leake (1978), three amphibole samples fall into Mhb category and four samples are plotted in Ts-Hbl array (Fig. 5). Amphibolites found in the symplectite (M3) are small in size as compared to the amphibolites found in the matrix (M2). Two Ts-Hbl and one Mhb are found in the matrix (M2) and one Ts-Hbl and one Mhb in the symplectite (M3). Epidote exists both as inclusions and in the matrix. Epidote found as inclusion in garnet is

smaller in size as compared to matrix epidote (Figs. 4a, b). The widespread plagioclase grains found in our samples are albite (Table 1; Figs. 4, 6).

Fig. 4. (a) Microscopic image of garnet possessing quartz and rutile inclusions. (b) Plane polarized image displaying amphibole, garnet, chlorite, epidote, and albite/quartz. (c) Plane polarized image of amphibole, albite and phengite in the matrix. Abbreviations of minerals are in accordance with Whitney and Evans (2010).

Fig. 5. Classification of amphiboles (Leake, 1978).

Phengite grains, found in matrix, are subhedral to anhedral and of medium size (Fig. 4c; Table 1). The high values of Si in mica (3.30 p.f.u) indicate phengite mineral. Phengite minerals are also found in the form of needles. Mineral assemblages in matrix (Grt + Hbl + Ab + Qz) and symplectite (Hbl + Ab + Qz) and the texture of amphibole in symplectite and matrix indicate the

representation of two metamorphic phases. Although we found various hornblende minerals as inclusions in garnet but we couldn't find suitable albite mineral as inclusions in garnet. Hence, we couldn't apply suitable geothermobarometers to calculate the prograde P-T conditions for our samples because of the absence of suitable mineral assemblages.

Fig. 6. Plagioclase classification diagram (after Klein and Hurlbut, 1993).

4.2 Geothermobarometry

The hornblende-plagioclase (HP) geothermometer (Holland and Blundy, 1994) and the garnet-hornblende-plagioclase-quartz (GHPQ) geobarometer (Dale et al., 2000) were used to calculate the metamorphic peak conditions of the garnet amphibolite. The random errors estimated were ± 40 °C (Holland and Blundy, 1994) and ± 1 kbar (Dale et al., 2000), respectively.

Fig. 7. Metamorphic P-T paths derived from two samples of Mozhugongka garnet amphibolite.

The geothermobarometers with no garnet are applied to the M3 assemblage. The hornblende-plagioclase geothermometer (Holland and Blundy, 1994) combined with the hornblende-plagioclase geobarometer (Molina et al., 2015) with random error of around ± 1.5 kbar, were used to calculate the P-T conditions of retrograde assemblages of garnet amphibolite. These two thermobarometers are chosen on the basis of mineral assemblages in symplectite and matrix. For peak metamorphic stage (M2), the calculated P-T results for sample D2093-N2 are 15.2 ± 1 kbar and 579 ± 20 °C, respectively. For retrograde metamorphic stage (M3), calculated P-T results for the same sample are 6 ± 0.5 kbar and 403 ± 10 °C, respectively (Fig. 7a). For sample D2093-N3, the computed P-T results for M2 stage are 16.1 ± 1 kbar and 552 ± 10 °C and calculated P-T conditions for M3 stage are 8.5 ± 1 kbar and 492 ± 30 °C, respectively (Fig. 7b).

5. Discussion

The presence of HP minerals like phengite indicates a possible high pressure metamorphism (Fig. 4c; Table 1). Sometimes, Na–Ca-amphibole found in symplectite along with garnet ring and plagioclase demonstrates a typical retrogression textures in these rocks (Singh et al., 2013). Amphibole composition can be affected by a variety of net transfer and exchange reactions, which can represent various metamorphic evolution stages of eclogites (Singh et al., 2013). Singh et al. (2013) divided the 3 metamorphic stages based on five mineral assemblages (i–v) attributing them to three different regimes: pre-UHP (association i), UHP (association ii, iii) and post-UHP (association iv, v). Out of all these associations, amphibole was reported from i, iii, iv and v. On the basis of chemistry and textural features of amphiboles, representation of more than one metamorphic assemblages have been displayed for various HP, UHP terranes around the world e.g. Western Gneiss Region, Norway, Krogh, 1980, 1982; Dabie Shan, China, Wang et al., 1992; Zhang et al., 1995; NE Caledonia, Clarke et al., 1997; Besshi district, Japan, Wallis and Aoya, 2000). Amphiboles have both calcic and sodic contents which may represent at least two stage metamorphism (Table 1). The P-T path of retrograde stage for Pangna blueschists can also be correlated with Mozhuogongka garnet amphibolites (Fig. 8), indicating that they may experience similar exhumation process. P-T path and their respective metamorphic and exhumation ages for Mozhuogongka amphibolites, Pangna blueschists, Songduo, Jilang and Bailang eclogites have been presented in Fig. 8 (Cheng et al., 2012, 2015; Liu et al., 2009; Yang et al., 2009).

Fig. 8. Estimated pressure temperature curve plotted using geothermobarometric results (modified after Cheng et al., 2015). Data source for Bailang eclogites (Cheng et al., 2015), Jilang eclogites (Cheng et al., 2012; Li et al., 2007, 2011), Songduo eclogites (Yang et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2011), Pangna blueschist (Liu et al., 2009) and our unpublished age results for Mozhugongka (MZH) amphibolites.

Songduo and Jilang eclogites show higher P-T conditions and elder ages of peak metamorphism as compared to Pangna blueschists, Bailang eclogites and Mozhugongka amphibolites, which probably indicates that the protoliths of Songduo and Jilang eclogites subducted and metamorphosed a little earlier than Pangna blueschists, Bailang eclogites and Mozhugongka amphibolites (Fig. 8). Songduo and Jilang eclogites (239 Ma. Yang et al., 2009; Cheng et al., 2012) also exhumed earlier as compared to Pangna blueschists (Permo-Triassic. Liu et al., 2009), Bailang eclogites (200 Ma. Cheng et al., 2015) and Mozhugongka garnet amphibolites (219 Ma. our unpublished material) (Fig. 8). The Songduo eclogites experienced exhumation in early Triassic (e.g., Zhang et al., 2019). In addition, both Mozhugongka

amphibolites and Bailang eclogites show similar geochemical features of within plate basalts (WPB) (unpublished data; Cheng et al., 2015). Hence Mozhugongka amphibolites can also be geochemically correlated with Bailang eclogites. Mozhugongka garnet amphibolites can possibly mark the western margin of Songduo metamorphic complex along with Pangna blueschist (Liu et al., 2009), since Pangna area is situated close to our study area. Mozhugongka garnet amphibolites P-T path for retrograde stage can be correlated with other four locality rocks (Fig. 8). They experienced probable similar retrograde metamorphic process from eclogite-facies during exhumation. Based on the geochronological data and similar P-T path (Fig. 8), Mozhugongka garnet amphibolites were possibly exhumed together with Pangna blueschists, Songduo, Bailang and Jilang eclogites (Cheng et al., 2012, 2015; Liu et al., 2009; Yang et al., 2009) and went through retrogression during exhumation. Mozhugongka garnet amphibolites can be geochemically and geochronologically compared with the Bailang eclogites, which mark the western extension of Songduo subduction system.

6. Conclusion

The observed mineral assemblages of Mozhugongka garnet amphibolites display two stages of metamorphism. The calculated P-T results for peak stage are between 15-16 kbar/552-579 °C and for retrograde stage, are between 6-8 kbar/403-492 °C. Mozhugongka garnet amphibolites, probably retrograde metamorphosed from eclogite, along with Pangna blueschists can possibly represent the westward extension of Songduo HP metamorphic complex.

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References

- Chengfa C, Nansheng C, Coward MP, Wanming D, Dewey JF, Gansser A, Harris NB, Chengwei J, Kidd WS, Leeder MR, Huan L. Preliminary conclusions of the Royal Society and Academia Sinica 1985 geotraverse of Tibet. *Nature*. 1986 Oct;323(6088):501-7.
- Cheng, H., Liu, Y., Vervoort, J.D., Lu, H., 2015. Combined U–Pb, Lu–Hf, Sm–Nd and Ar–Ar multichronometric dating on the Bailang eclogite constrains the closure timing of the Paleo-Tethys Ocean in the Lhasa terrane, Tibet. *Gondwana Research* 28, 1482–1499.
- Cheng, H., Zhang, C., Vervoort, J.D., Lu, H., Wang, C., Cao, D., 2012. Zircon U–Pb and garnet Lu–Hf geochronology of eclogites from the Lhasa block, Tibet. *Lithos* 155, 341–359.
- Clarke, G.L., Aitchison, J.C. and Cluzel, D., 1997. Eclogites and blueschists of the Pam Peninsula, NE New Caledonia: a reappraisal. *Journal of Petrology*, 38(7), pp.843-876.
- Dale, J., Holland, T., and Powell, R., 2000. Hornblende-garnet-plagioclase thermobarometry: a natural assemblage calibration of the thermodynamics of hornblende: *Contrib. Miner. Petrol*, v. 140, p. 353–362.
- Droop G. T. R.. A general equation for estimating fe³⁺ concentrations in ferromagnesian silicates and oxides from microprobe analyses, using stoichiometric criteria. *Mineralogical Magazine*, 51(361), 431-435.
- Erdman, M. E., & Lee, C. T. A., 2014. Oceanic-and continental-type metamorphic terranes: Occurrence and exhumation mechanisms: *Earth-Science Reviews*, 139, 33-46.
- Geng, Q., Pan, G., Zheng, L., Chen, Z., Fisher, R. D., Sun, Z., Ou, C., Dong, H., Wang, X., Li, S. and Lou, X., 2006. The Eastern Himalayan syntaxis: major tectonic domains, ophiolitic melanges and geologic evolution. *Journal of Asian Earth Sciences*, 27(3), pp.265-285
- Geological Survey Institute of Xizang, 2007, 1:250000 geological map, unpublished.
- Holland, T., and Blundy, J., 1994. Non-ideal interactions in calcic amphiboles and their bearing on amphibole-plagioclase thermometry: *Contrib. Miner. Petrol*, v. 116, p. 433–447.
- Jin, X., Zhang, Y.X., Zhou, X.Y., Zhang, K.J., Li, Z.W., Khalid, S.B., Hu, J.C., Lu, L. and Sun, W.D., 2019. Protoliths and tectonic implications of the newly discovered Triassic Baqing eclogites, central Tibet: Evidence from geochemistry, Sr-Nd isotopes and geochronology. *Gondwana Research*, 69, pp.144-162.
- Klein, C.J. and Hurlbut, S., 1993. *Manual of Mineralogy*, 21ème Ed.
- Krogh, E.J., 1980. Geochemistry and petrology of glaucophane-bearing eclogites and associated rocks from Sunnfjord, western Norway. *Lithos*, 13(4), pp.355-380.
- Krogh, E.J., 1982. Metamorphic evolution of Norwegian country-rock eclogites, as deduced from mineral inclusions and compositional zoning in garnets. *Lithos*, 15(4), pp.305-321.
- Leake, B., 1978. Nomenclature of amphiboles: *Canadian Mineralogist*, v. 16.
- Li, T.F., Yang, J.S., Li, Z.L., Xu, X.Z., Ren, Y.F., Wang, R.C., Zhang, W.L., 2007. Petrography and metamorphic evolution of the Sumdo eclogite, Qinghai-Tibetan Plateau: *Geological Bulletin of China* 26, 1310–1326 (in Chinese with English abstract).
- Li, H.Q., Xu, Z.Q., Yang, J.S., Tang, Z.M., Yang, M., 2011. Syn-collision exhumation of Sumdo eclogite in the Lhasa terrane, Tibet: Evidences from structural deformation and Ar–Ar geochronology: *Earth Science Frontiers* 18, 66–78 (in Chinese with English abstract).
- Liu, Y., Liu, H., Theye, T. and Massonne, H.J., 2009. Evidence for oceanic subduction at the NE Gondwana margin during Permo–Triassic times. *Terra Nova*, 21(3), pp.195-202.
- Molina, J.F., Moreno, J.A., Castro, A., Rodriguez, C., and Fershtater, G.B., 2015. Calcic amphibole thermobarometry in metamorphic and igneous rocks: new calibrations based on

- plagioclase/amphibole Al-Si partitioning and amphibole/liquid Mg partitioning: *Lithos*, v. 232, p. 286–305.
- Ring, U. & Glodny, J., 2010. No need for lithospheric extension for exhuming (U)HP rocks by normal faulting: *Journal of the Geological Society, London* 167, 1–4.
- Singh, P., Saikia, A., Pant, N.C. and Verma, P.K., 2013. Insights into the P–T evolution path of Tso Moriri eclogites of the north-western Himalayas: constraints on the geodynamic evolution of the region. *Journal of Earth System Science*, 122(3), pp.677-698.
- Smith, D.C., 1988. A review of the peculiar mineralogy of the ‘Norwegian coesite/eclogite province’ with crystal-chemical, petrological, geochemical and geodynamical notes and an extensive bibliography. In: Smith, D.C. (eds) *Eclogites and Eclogite-facies Rocks. Developments in Petrology*, 12, 1-206.
- Wallis, S. and Aoya, M., 2000. A re - evaluation of eclogite facies metamorphism in SW Japan: proposal for an eclogite nappe. *Journal of Metamorphic Geology*, 18(6), pp.653-664.
- Wang, B., Xie, C.M., Fan, J.J., Wang, M., Yu, Y.P., Dong, Y.C., and Hao, Y.J., 2019. Genesis and tectonic setting of Middle Permian OIB-type mafic rocks in the Sumdo area, southern Lhasa terrane: *Lithos*, v. 324, p. 429-438. doi.org/10.1016/j.lithos.2018.11.015
- Wang, X., Liou, J.G. and Maruyama, S., 1992. Coesite-bearing eclogites from the Dabie Mountains, central China: Petrogenesis, PT paths, and implications for regional tectonics. *The Journal of Geology*, 100(2), pp.231-250.
- Whitney, D.L., and Evans, B.W., 2010. Abbreviations for names of rock-forming minerals: *American mineralogist*, v. 95, p. 185-187.
- Wu, C.M., Lu, J.S., and Wang, G.D., 2014. Determination of pressure-temperature conditions of retrograde symplectic assemblages in granulites and amphibolites: *Global J. Earth Sci. Eng.*, v. 1(2), p. 71–83.
- Xu, Z., Li, H. and Yang, J., 2006. An orogenic plateau-the orogenic collage and orogenic types of the Qinghai-Tibet plateau. *Earth Science Frontiers*, 13(4), p.1.
- Yang, J., Xu, Z., Geng, Q. R., Li, Z., Xu, X., Li, T., Ren, Y., Li, H., Cai, Z., and Liang, F., 2006. A possible new HP/UHP (?) metamorphic belt in China: discovery of eclogite in the Lhasa Terrane, Tibet: *Acta Geologica Sinica*, v. 80, p. 1787-1792.
- Yang, J., Xu, Z., Li, Z., Xu, X., Li, T., Ren, Y., Li, H., Chen, S., Robinson, P., 2009. Discovery of an eclogite belt in the Lhasa block, Tibet: a newborder for paleo-Tethys? *Journal of Asian Earth Sciences* 34, 76–89.
- Yin, A. and Harrison, T.M., 2000. Geologic evolution of the Himalayan-Tibetan orogen. *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences*, 28(1), pp.211-280.
- Yin, A., 2006. Cenozoic tectonic evolution of the Himalayan orogen as constrained by along-strike variation of structural geometry, exhumation history, and foreland sedimentation. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 76(1-2), pp.1-131.
- Zhang, C., Bader, T., van Roermund, H., Yang, J., Shen, T., Qiu, T., and Li, P., 2019. The metamorphic evolution and tectonic significance of the Sumdo HP–UHP metamorphic terrane, central-south Lhasa Block, Tibet: *Geological Society, London, Special Publications*, v. 474, p. 209-229.
- Zhang, D.D., Zhang, L.F., Zhao, Z.D., 2011. A study of metamorphism of Sumdo eclogite in Tibet, China. *Earth Science Frontiers* 18, 116–126 (in Chinese with English abstract).
- Zhang, K. and Tang, X., 2009. Eclogites in the interior of the Tibetan Plateau and their geodynamic implications. *Chinese Science Bulletin*, 54(15), p.2556.

- Zhang, K.J., et al., 2012, Late Mesozoic tectonic evolution and growth of the Tibetan plateau prior to the Indo–Asian collision, *Earth–Science Reviews*.
- Zhang, R.Y., Hirajima, T., Banno, S., Cong, B. and Liou, J.G., 1995. Petrology of ultrahigh–pressure rocks from the southern Su–Lu region, eastern China. *Journal of Metamorphic Geology*, 13(6), pp.659-675
- Zhang, Y.X., Jin, X., Zhang, K.J., Sun, W.D., Liu, J.M., Zhou, X.Y. and Yan, L.L., 2018. Newly discovered Late Triassic Baqing eclogite in central Tibet indicates an anticlockwise West–East Qiangtang collision. *Scientific reports*, 8(1), pp.1-12.
- Zhang, Y.X. and Zhang, K.J., 2017. Early Permian Qiangtang flood basalts, northern Tibet, China: A mantle plume that disintegrated northern Gondwana?. *Gondwana Research*, 44, pp.96-108.
- Zhang, Z.M., Dong, X., Liu, F., Lin, Y.H., Yan, R. and Santosh, M., 2012. Tectonic evolution of the Amdo terrane, central Tibet: Petrochemistry and zircon U-Pb geochronology. *The Journal of Geology*, 120(4), pp.431-451.
- Zhu, D.C., Zhao, Z.D., Niu, Y., Dilek, Y. and Mo, X.X., 2011a. Lhasa terrane in southern Tibet came from Australia. *Geology*, 39(8), pp.727-730.
- Zhu, D.C., Zhao, Z.D., Niu, Y., Mo, X.X., Chung, S.L., Hou, Z.Q., Wang, L.Q. and Wu, F.Y., 2011b. The Lhasa Terrane: record of a microcontinent and its histories of drift and growth. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 301(1-2), pp.241-255.
- Zhu, D.C., Zhao, Z.D., Niu, Y., Dilek, Y., Hou, Z.Q. and Mo, X.X., 2013. The origin and pre-Cenozoic evolution of the Tibetan Plateau. *Gondwana Research*, 23(4), pp.1429-1454.

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